

PhD at EMBL

Zuzana Koskova

PhD Student at EMBL Heidelberg

14/09/2023

2016-2021

BSc & MSc

University Heidelberg

2021

Erasmus Internship

Francis Crick Institute

2022

Erasmus Internship

Karolinska Institutet

2022 - now

EMBL International PhD Programme

Unique in the world and waiting for you!

PhD

EMBL Heidelberg

Why I chose EMBL

Cutting-edge technologies

Core facilities

Ambitious large-scale projects

Public engagement

Seminars, courses, conferences

Why I chose EMBL

International environment

Collaborations

Friendly culture

PhD project: RNAs on mitotic chromosomes

Research group of Dr. Sara Cuylen-Haering
in the Cell Biology and Biophysics Unit

Magenta: chromatin

Green: Ki-67

Collaborations: Image-enabled cell sorting

FACS

Microscopy

Enrichment of rare cell types:

- cell size
- protein expression

- High throughput
- Cell Sorting
- No subcellular resolution

Identification of subcellular structures

- Subcellular resolution
- Low throughput
- Lacks isolation/enrichment capabilities

Imaging-enabled cell sorting

Collaborations: Image-enabled cell sorting

Flow + Image Acquisition

Analysis of Image Parameters

Cell Sorting

- High-speed image-acquisition of cells in flow
- Near instant analysis of fluorescence signal image features
- High-speed cell-sorting based on parameter gating in real time (15,000 cells/sec)

Collaborations: Image-enabled cell sorting

Terra Kuhn

RESEARCH TECHNOLOGY

High-speed fluorescence image-enabled cell sorting

Daniel Schraivogel¹, Terra M. Kuhn^{2†}, Benedikt Rauscher^{1†}, Marta Rodriguez-Martinez^{1†}, Malte Paulsen^{3†}, Keegan Owsley⁴, Aaron Middlebrook⁴, Christian Tischer⁵, Beáta Ramasz³, Diana Ordoñez-Rueda³, Martina Dees², Sara Cuylen-Haering^{2*}, Eric Diebold^{4*}, Lars M. Steinmetz^{1,6,7*}

What I'm doing at EMBL

Ambitious project

Science Education & Public Engagements

Collaborations

Lab Sustainability

Registration for the 2024 Winter Recruitment is now open.

In order to apply, please fill in the

(online application is compulsory).

2024 Winter Recruitment timeline:

Application opens	August 2023
Application submission deadline	09 October 2023, 23:59 CEST
Reference deadline	11 October 2023, 23:59 CEST
Written application results	Will be announced around mid-November 2023
Interview dates:	
Screening interviews (online)	Between 23 October – 9 November 2023
Virtual Panel Assessment	TBC
In-person interviews	22 – 26 January 2024 (at EMBL-EBI and EMBL Barcelona, Grenoble, Hamburg and Rome) 29 January – 1 February 2024 (at EMBL Heidelberg)
Expected start date	Flexible; by October 2024 at the latest

PhD programme overview

PhD programme overview

- 8 weeks
- Intense lectures and practicals
- Getting to know EMBL infrastructure / core facilities
- Social events
- Networking / friendships with peers and all EMBL staff
- PhD symposium organized by 2nd year PhD students

Register Now!
in our website

25th EMBL PhD Symposium

POWER OF MANY
COLLECTIVE BEHAVIOUR
ACROSS SCALES

EMBL | 20-22 November 2023 | Heidelberg, Germany

Registration deadline: 06 October 2023

Travel grants & reduced fees to join online!

Confirmed Speakers:

Zev Gartner – UCSF
Gray Camp – IHB Basel
Claudia Valsechi – IMB Mainz
Ben Engel – Biozentrum Basel
Gilles Laurent – MPI Brain Research
Rebecca Sepela – Harvard University
Paola Scaffidi – Francis Crick Institute
Fei Chen – Broad Institute MIT/Harvard
Verena Ruprecht – CRG Barcelona
Jenny Fung – MPI / Duke University
Manolis Kellis – Broad Institute MIT/Harvard
Samantha Stephens – University of Queensland

And others...

PhD programme overview

2.7%

Acceptance rate
of applicants

~ 50–60

New PhD
students
admitted each
year

~ 50

Nationalities
represented
among PhD
students

3.95 years

Average time to
submission of
thesis

1.3

First-author
papers *per* PhD
student

92%

Completion rate
of thesis among
PhD students

Online application

Open application for the EMBL International PhD Programme!

No application for a specific lab!

List of hiring group leaders only published before interviews!

Online application: apply for specific units

Heidelberg, DE

Cell biology and biophysics

Scientists in this unit use multidisciplinary approaches to investigate the molecular and biophysical mechanisms that enable cells to function.

Structural and computational biology

Scientists in this unit use integrated structural and computational techniques to study biology at scales from molecular structures to organismal communities.

Genome biology

Scientists in the Genome Biology Unit use and develop cutting-edge methods to study how information across different molecular layers (DNA, RNA, Proteins, metabolites) are regulated, processed, and utilised, and how their variation leads to different phenotypes, including disease.

Developmental biology

Research in the Developmental Biology Unit is focused on understanding the origin, development, and evolution of organisms and their communities.

Hinxton, UK

Bioinformatics research

Researchers at EMBL-EBI make sense of vast, complex biological datasets produced using new and emerging technologies in molecular biology.

Rome, IT

Epigenetics and neurobiology

At EMBL Rome, scientists explore the connections between genome, environment, and neural function.

Hamburg, DE / Grenoble, FR

Structural biology

At its sites in [Hamburg](#) and [Grenoble](#), EMBL provides its researchers and hundreds of external users each year with access to world-leading sources of X-ray and cryo-electron microscopy facilities, enabling them to study the structures of biological molecules.

Barcelona, ES

Tissue biology and disease modelling

Scientists at EMBL Barcelona use advanced technologies to observe, manipulate, and model how changes in genes percolate through cells, tissues, and organs, in health and disease.

Online application: information about you

- Education path, certificates, grades
- Your favourite research topic
- Your motivation to do a PhD
- EMBL labs you'd be interested in
- Your favourite publication
- References

Pre-screening interviews

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- Usually one group leader per interested unit
- Questions:
 - Why do you want to do a PhD?
 - Why biology/specific field?
 - Experience?
 - How did you solve a difficult situation in your project?
 - Team player / individual?
- Space for your questions

Panel assessment

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- Panel of 4 EMBL group leaders
- 30 minutes
- Highly dependent on the group leaders
- Assessing:
 - Biological knowledge / familiarity with methods
 - Experience
 - Motivation
 - Communication / language skills

In-person interviews

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- Interviews scheduled for you
- Contact Graduate Office if you want extra interviews
- Amount of interviews depends on
 - Number of interesting/interested units
 - Interviews only by hiring group leaders / whole units
 - Additional interviews with lab members

How to find a good PhD lab?

- Talk to current and former lab members
- Ask the PI about their motivation / supervision style
- Know your strength / weaknesses and communicate them
- Make sure you can have a happy life in the city / country

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For PhD students in Slovakia

Scientific Visitor Programme

Enabling external scientists and students to benefit from new collaborations, technologies and state-of-the-art equipment

EMBL Fellowships:

- [Corporate Partnership Programme Fellowships](#)
- [Christian Boulin fellowships](#) for Core Facility visits
- [EMBL-UNESCO Residency in Infection Biology](#) (for women scientists from Africa)

External fellowships (please check your eligibility for these):

- [EMBO Scientific Exchange grants](#)
- [DANEMO fellowships](#) (for Denmark based researchers)
- [Innovation Campus Heidelberg-Mannheim](#) (only if visiting EMBL Heidelberg)
- [Boehringer Ingelheim Fonds travel grants](#)
- [EMBL Australia short term travel grants](#)
- [IUBMB Fellowships](#)
- [MSCA Staff Exchanges](#)

Contact

Scientific Visitor Programme

European Molecular Biology Laboratory
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Verena Ruprecht – CRG Barcelona
Jenny Fung – MPI / Duke University
Manolis Kellis – Broad Institute MIT/Harvard
Samantha Stephens – University of Queensland

And some others...

**Thank you for
your attention!**

Contact me / ask me anything at:

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<https://www.linkedin.com/in/zuzana-koskova/>

